

Multi-Criteria HVAC Control Optimization

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Abstract—Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems consist one of the main elements that have a significant impact to both occupants' comfort and energy consumption in tertiary buildings, affecting therefore productivity and operational cost respectively. Energy consumption depends on occupant comfort through the calculation of the thermal comfort function, a function which derives from an extended analysis that takes into account various parameters such as temperature, humidity, air velocity, activity and clothing. This paper examines the implementation of a multi-criteria algorithm for optimizing operational control of HVAC systems, by integrating multiple real-time condition variables as input and targeting maximization of occupants' comfort satisfaction and minimization of energy consumption as output. As added value, the proposed framework allows its users to configure themselves the balance between comfort and consumption by adjusting specific thresholds. The effectiveness of the optimization algorithm is presented through the real-time operation of an HVAC system in an office building. Experimental results are presented and conclusions regarding the value of the HVAC optimal operational control are derived.

Keywords— Heating, ventilation and air conditioning; Thermal comfort; Multi-criteria control algorithm; Thermal Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

World energy consumption has become a major concern to scientific and political communities [1]. In EU countries, primary energy consumption in buildings represents about 40% of total energy consumption and depending on the countries more than half of this energy is used by systems preserving comfortable indoor climate conditions i.e. Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems [2]. Therefore, the need for implementing methods and tools for energy management in the building sector is evident. From a technological point of view, it is estimated that the use of technologies such as Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS / BMS / EMS), can offer energy savings up to 20% in the building sector [2]. On the other hand, since people spend 80% of their lifetime in buildings, a healthy and comfortable environment is important for occupants' well-being and productivity [3]. To maintain an optimal equilibrium between both aspects, building loads' operation requires optimization mechanisms in real-time operation, with HVAC, as the main asset for thermal comfort management, introducing a complex equipment, usually employed for maintaining satisfactory comfort while consuming significant amounts of energy [2].

Unfortunately, B(E)MS have, generally, failed to fully optimize energy consumption in commercial buildings without

just barely maintaining occupants' comfort levels [4]. Computational Intelligence (CI), including Neural Networks (NNs), Fuzzy Logic Systems (FLSs), and Genetic Algorithms (GAs), have been widely utilized for HVAC control.

NNs have been widely used for energy prediction and modeling in various types of buildings [5]. However, there are still aspects that haven't been explored either in residential buildings or in terms of occupant comfort and HVAC operational cost. In some cases, NN can be further enriched by additional technologies to improve the optimization process. In [6], a Genetic Algorithm is used along Artificial NN in order to provide an optimization process that uses self-tuning HVAC component models, resulting cooling energy savings up to 11%.

The problem of NNs is that they are regarded as "black boxes". FLSs can overcome this problem as they are based on human readable fuzzy membership functions and rules that can describe the performance of the system. A lot of research has been using FLSs for intelligent buildings and HVAC systems, going a few decades back, when [7] introduced the design of fuzzy rule-based controller for the mixing box of an air handling unit, and [8] presented the advantages of the fuzzy control techniques in satisfying the users' preferences.

Just like NNs, FLSs aren't without drawbacks; there is a need for parameters learning mechanisms, which can be met with learning techniques like NNs and GAs to determine the variables of the fuzzy systems. An example of this approach is presented in [9], where building comfort improvement was achieved by adjusting the fan-coils air flow rate through a neuro-fuzzy control system. In another approach [10], fuzzy-neural systems have been used to bridge results extracted from building energy consumption simplified and detailed estimation methods. Besides NN, a GA-based classifier system has been employed in [11] to enable an air-conditioning controller to learn from its own experience the optimal control strategy against a given performance evaluation scheme.

However, according to [4], solutions to that point with integrated FLSs, NNs, or GAs were not yet able to provide sufficient optimization models for building operation. To address this, [4] presented a novel agent-based system (Intelligent Control of Energy - ICE) for energy management in commercial buildings, where within each agent different CI techniques are employed (including FLSs, NNs and Gas) to "learn" buildings thermal response to various variables such as weather conditions, internal occupancy requirements and building plant responses. Each of these techniques may be

more or less accurate depending on environmental conditions. By selecting the appropriate CI based algorithm which works in real-time with the building's existing BEMS, it's possible to minimize the building's energy demand. Following this work, authors in [3] present a multi-agent based intelligent control system for achieving effective energy and comfort management in a building environment.

To our knowledge, current literature lacks from an unsupervised control system capable of operating in real-time continuously without requiring any external human intervention, and is adjustable to occupants' indirect feedback. In this work, we propose a deterministic algorithm, which aims to optimize real-time operation of an HVAC system. In practice, it optimizes an objective function in which various criteria, crucial for the HVAC operation, are implemented by introducing weights for each one of them. These weights are not determined by any expert or using any "trial and error" methodology, but rather they are calculated presenting an ideal balance among the various criteria. The objective function simulates the divergence of the value of each criterion from its ideal one. In conclusion, the proposed algorithm optimizes the real-time operation of the HVAC system, minimizing the objective function and therefore making the values of the criteria reach their target ones, which are specified in advance.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the performance of the HVAC systems, while Section III presents the proposed deterministic weight calculation algorithm. Section IV presents the experimental results, while conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. HEATING VENTILATION AND AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEMS

An HVAC system is a rather complex set of components that have as a main goal to optimally adjust indoor environmental conditions towards providing thermal comfort and acceptable air quality. In modern intelligent buildings, a sophisticated control system should provide excellent control [2], which is highly dependent on the control system's performance criteria.

A. Performance Criteria

The operational performance of the HVAC can be optimized according to the following criteria:

- M_1 Occupants' Thermal Comfort. It is determined by the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV).
- M_2 Electrical Consumption (in Wh) of the HVACs.

B. Thermal Comfort Analysis

Based on [12] where the thermal comfort analysis has been validated, occupants' thermal comfort poses the most important factor for the optimization of the HVAC control system. For accessing the thermal comfort of a human being a set of variables needs to be taken under consideration, including not only air temperature, but also mean radiant temperature, relative air velocity, humidity, activity level and clothing resistance. The combined quantitative influence of the above parameters was not known until the "Comfort Equation" definition by Fanger [13].

The mean core temperature of an adult human being is approximately 37°C and generally it is not influenced even by large variations in ambient temperature. By converting chemical energy of food into work and heat, the internal temperature (core-temperature) can be kept constant, but only if there is balance between the heat produced by the body and the heat lost to the environment. It is known that under normal and balanced conditions, the heat energy produced by the metabolism equals the rate of heat transferred from the body by conduction, convection, radiation, evaporation and respiration [14]. The fundamental thermodynamic process in heat exchange between man and his environment may be described by the general heat balance equation:

$$M - W = C + R + E_{sk} + (C_{res} + E_{res}). \quad (1)$$

where the external work W (W/m^2) is small and is generally ignored under most situations. The internal energy production M (W/m^2) is determined by metabolic activity. C (W/m^2) is the heat loss by convection. R (W/m^2) is the heat loss by thermal radiation. E_{sk} (W/m^2) is the heat loss by evaporation from the skin. C_{res} (W/m^2) and E_{res} (W/m^2) are the sensible and the evaporation heat loss due to respiration respectively. The convection heat transfer C (W/m^2) from the human body to the environment is given by:

$$C = f_{cl} \cdot h_c (T_{cl} - T_a), \quad (2)$$

where T_{cl} (°C) is the clothing surface temperature and T_a (°C) is the ambient air temperature. The heat transfer coefficient h_c (W/m^2K) depends on the air velocity V_a (m/s) across the body and consequently also upon the position of the person and orientation to the air current. An approximate value of h_c during forced convection can be evaluated as:

$$h_c = 12.1 \cdot V_a^{0.5}. \quad (3)$$

The clothing area factor f_{cl} is expressed as follows:

$$f_{cl} = 1.05 + 0.1 \cdot I_{cl}, \quad (4)$$

where I_{cl} is the thermal insulation of clothing. The insulation of clothing is often expressed in *clo* units, but it is used in SI units as R_{cl} in calculations:

$$R_{cl} = 0.155 \cdot I_{cl} \quad (5)$$

The rate of heat transfer by radiation R (W/m^2) depends on the mean temperature of surrounding surfaces, skin or clothing surface temperature and properties of clothing (or skin) and surrounding surfaces. The radiation heat transfer between the body and surrounding surfaces is given as follows:

$$R = \sigma \cdot \varepsilon_{cl} \cdot f_{cl} \cdot F_{vf} \cdot [(T_{cl} + 273.15)^4 - (T_r + 273.15)^4], \quad (6)$$

where ε_{cl} is the emissivity of the clothing. The emissivity of the clothing and skin is very close to that of a black body and thus has a value of nearly 1. F_{vf} is the view factor between the body and the surrounding surface, which determines the effective area of the body for radiation, which is consequently less than the total surface area usually about 75% of the total.

σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, which has the numerical value of $5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}^4$. T_γ ($^\circ\text{C}$) is the radiant temperature. The surrounding surface temperature is usually at a low temperature level. Thus the temperatures of the surrounding surfaces can be taken as approximately ambient air temperature T_a ($^\circ\text{C}$).

The respiration heat loss is divided into evaporative heat loss (latent heat) and sensible heat loss. The rate of the heat transfer by respiration is usually at the lower level beside the other rates of the heat transfer. This rate is given by:

$$C_{res} + E_{res} = 0.014 \cdot M \cdot (34 - T_a) + 0.0173 \cdot M \cdot (5.87 - P_a) \quad (7)$$

where P_a (P_a) is the partial vapor pressure. The partial vapor pressure is calculated using the following equation:

$$RH = P_a / P_s \quad (8)$$

where the RH is the relative humidity of the ambient air and P_s (P_s) is the saturation pressure of water vapor. The saturation pressure of water vapor is calculated as follows:

$$P_s = [0.782 + 2.962 \cdot \frac{T_a}{100} + 6.290 \cdot \left(\frac{T_a}{100}\right)^{2.325}]^2 \quad (9)$$

The heat loss by evaporation of perspiration from the skin is considered as the rate of the heat loss by evaporation, and it always constitutes a rejection of heat from body. The evaporation loss is dependent upon the mass transfer coefficient and the air humidity ratio for a given body surface temperature. The heat loss by evaporation is made up of two, the insensible heat loss by skin diffusion and the heat loss by regulatory sweating. This rate can be calculated by:

$$E_{sk} = 3.05 \cdot (5.73 - 0.007 \cdot M - P_a) + 0.42 \cdot (M - 58.15) \quad (10)$$

The conduction heat transfer through the clothing takes place in order to the different temperatures of its inner and outer surfaces. The conduction heat transfer from the inner surface to the outer surface of the clothing is defined as follows:

$$C_k = (T_{sk} - T_{cl}) / R_{cl} \quad (11)$$

where T_{sk} ($^\circ\text{C}$) is the skin temperature. This heat transfer from the clothing's outer surface is further transferred to the environment by convection and radiation heat losses. Thus:

$$C_k = C + R \quad (12)$$

As the heat energy flow through the clothing in the steady-state is determined by (12) the clothing temperature can be determined using the (11) as presented below:

$$T_{cl} = T_{sk} - R_{cl} \cdot (C + R) \Rightarrow$$

$$T_{cl} = T_{sk} - R_{cl} \cdot \left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_{cl} \cdot h_c \cdot (T_{cl} - T_a) + \sigma \cdot \varepsilon_{cl} \cdot f_{cl} \cdot F_{vf} \cdot \\ \left[(T_{cl} + 273.15)^4 - (T_r + 273.15)^4 \right] \end{array} \right\} \quad (13)$$

T_{sk} ($^\circ\text{C}$) is defined as follows:

$$T_{sk} = 35.7 - 0.0275 \cdot M \quad (14)$$

Finally, the PMV value is defined as [13]:

$$PMV = (0.303 \cdot e^{-0.036 \cdot M} + 0.028) \cdot L \quad (15)$$

where L is defined as follows:

$$L = M - W - C - R - E_{sk} - (C_{res} + E_{res}) \quad (16)$$

According to ASHRAE a PMV value of +3 is hot, a value of -3 is cold, whereas a value of 0 is where most people feel comfortable in terms of a thermal sensation scale. Taking that into account and after normalizing these values in a scale 0-1, the desirable occupants' thermal comfort will be the one closest to 0.

III. DETERMINISTIC CONVERGENCE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The main objective of this work is the formulation of a multi-criteria algorithm, which optimizes the operation of the HVAC system through an objective function. It adjusts the importance of each criterion in the objective function according to the difference between its current and its target value. More specifically, it decreases the importance of each criterion, whenever it reaches its target value and it increases its importance (penalize) whenever its value diverges from its target one [2]. Additionally, the need of the implementation of various criteria in the same objective function has concluded in the introduction of weights (w_i). Finally, a normalization process of the examined criteria takes place before the implementation of these criteria in the objective function. The aforementioned process aims to define the position of each criterion in its range of values.

A. Objective Function

Taking all the above into consideration the objective function is formulated accordingly:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i^m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i \quad (17)$$

where N is the number of criteria, M_i is the criterion on which the optimization of the electrical devices operation (HVACs) is dependent, w_i is a specific weight dynamically calculated for each criteria, m is a fuzziness coefficient, and $\delta(M_i)$ is the penalization function that defines the importance of each criterion. Since the adaptation values of the criteria decrease as their current values tend to reach their target values, the minimization of the objective function is the main goal of our proposed algorithm.

B. Penalization Function

The penalization function is formulated accordingly:

- When $g_i > i_i$

$$\delta(M_i) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0, M_i < g_i \\ \frac{M_i - g_i}{M_i - M_i \cdot p_i}, g_i \leq M_i \end{array} \right\} \quad (18)$$

- When $g_i \leq i_i$

$$\delta(M_i) = \left. \begin{cases} 0, M_i \leq g_i \\ \frac{M_i - g_i}{i_i - g_i}, g_i < M_i < i_i \\ \frac{M_i - i_i}{M_i - M_i \cdot p_i} + 1, i_i \leq M_i \end{cases} \right\}, \quad (19)$$

where i_i , g_i and p_i are the initial value, the target value and the penalty value of each criterion i respectively.

The adaptation value of the current value of each criterion is configured according to its current, its initial, its target and its penalty value. As mentioned above, the adaptation value penalizes any criterion which diverges from its target value. The aim of the penalty value is to allow the user to determine the importance of each criterion in the optimization of the control of the HVAC system. Its range is $[0,1]$ with 0 to represent the lowest and 1 highest importance.

C. Weight calculation

In order to calculate each weight of each criterion in each optimization procedure, it is determined that their summation should be equal to one.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N w_i = 1, \quad (20)$$

$$(17) \Rightarrow F = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i^m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i + \lambda \cdot (1 - \sum_{i=1}^N w_i), \quad (21)$$

where λ is a constant. Using the summation of the weights and equating the differentiation of the objective function to zero the calculation of the weights can be confronted, as presented below.

$$(21) \Rightarrow \frac{dF}{dw_i} = 0 \Rightarrow m \cdot w_i^{m-1} \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i - \lambda = 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$w_i = \left(\frac{\lambda}{m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}}, \quad (22)$$

$$(20) \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\lambda}{m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}} = 1 \Rightarrow$$

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i)^{\frac{-1}{m-1}} \right)^{m-1}}, \quad (23)$$

$$(22) \Rightarrow w_i = \frac{(m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i)^{\frac{-1}{m-1}}}{\sum_{i=1}^N (m \cdot \delta(M_i) \cdot M_i)^{\frac{-1}{m-1}}}, \quad (24)$$

D. Criteria Normalization

In order to scale objectives into an identical order of magnitude, a normalization process is usually needed in weighted aggregation methods. The normalization of the criteria is presented below:

$$M_i^{norm} = \frac{M_i - M_i^{\min}}{M_i^{\max} - M_i^{\min}}. \quad (25)$$

E. Methodology

The optimization of the HVAC control system is fulfilled finding the appropriate temperature set-points, which will satisfy the examined performance criteria of the HVAC operation. Assuming that the HVAC operates in a specific temperature set-point, we evaluate the scenarios of increasing, decreasing, and keeping the same temperature set-points concluding in the scenario, which minimizes the objective function. Aiming to maintain the system stability even in an implicit way, we examine firstly the set-points resulting from increasing and decreasing the initial set-point by one, two and three. For each potential temperature set-point, the HVAC operation is simulated providing us the energy consumption and the resulting room temperature, which is used in the PMV calculation. These criteria configure the value of the objective function. This methodology is repeated for each potential set-point and concludes when the objective function is minimized.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Pilot description

The proposed algorithm has been tested in an existing building control system, which is integrated in the main building of the Information Technologies Institute, where a multi-sensorial network exists. This system provides a holistic approach in the way to overcome the existing limitations and deficiencies of current building energy management systems and offers an integrated solution for real-time automated unsupervised building operation towards reducing energy consumption based on building occupancy and occupants' preferences. The term unsupervised is used to define that the system once initiated runs and controls building assets autonomously without requiring any human intervention. The operation of the building control system is supported by a set of hardware and software low-level components, which are set up in order to fulfil the information flow from the sensors to the system. A multi-sensorial network has been installed in the building providing a variety of sensors for real-time information which is necessary for the extraction of the current context, further allowing the collection of historical data as required for model creation, while load actuators enable control access to the various devices. The multi-sensorial network installed at the building allows information

extraction over environmental conditions (e.g. temperature, luminance, and humidity), occupancy, consumption, and device operational status.

B. Definition of the default values in the algorithm

Target values of the performance criteria of the HVAC:

- Occupants' Thermal Comfort: $g_1=0$. Optimal value of the PMV, which corresponds to neutral thermal comfort.
- Electrical Consumption: $g_2=0$. The optimal value is the minimum potential. Although zero cannot lead to the appropriate occupants' thermal comfort, it is the ideal value for the minimization of the electrical consumption.
- Fuzziness Coefficient $m=2$, as the most frequently used value **Error! Reference source not found.**

Penalty parameters (with a range of [0, 1]):

- Occupants' Thermal Comfort: $p_1=0.5$.
- Electrical Consumption: $p_2=0.05$.

Parameters used in the Thermal Comfort Analysis [12]:

- $M=70W/m^2$: Typical metabolic rate.
- $RH=50\%$: Typical value of air velocity.
- $I_{cl}=0.75clo$: Clothing typical value.
- $V_a=0.1m/s$: Typical value of air velocity.

C. Experiments

The experiments performed in the context of this research work took place in a Meeting Room that can accommodate up to 16 occupants. This space was selected due to the fact that its thermal zone is not greatly affected by the other corresponding zones in the proximity of the room. The experiments are performed in a typical work day in summer, where the outside temperature ranges from 27°C to 35°C.

D. Results

In Fig. 1 the temperature set-points that our algorithm proposes for each optimization procedure to the HVAC system are shown. Additionally, in the same diagram the temperatures measured at the HVAC side, the Room temperatures and the occupants' thermal comfort incurred by the respective temperature set-points are presented.

The temperature set-points have an immediate impact on the HVAC temperatures, while their impact on the Room temperatures is time and quantity constrained. The HVAC temperatures present great alteration even with the set-point modifications of 1°C. The maximum of this alteration can reach even 4°C. However, according to this figure even without any change to the set-point, the HVAC temperature alters due to the external conditions outside either the room or the building. This immediate impact is the reason that the HVAC temperature is used in the PMV calculation, as described in Section III. On the contrary, the Room temperature constitutes a more stable unit. Undoubtedly, this

observation derives from the fact that the modification of a room temperature is time-consuming.

Fig. 1. Temperature Set-Points, HVAC Temperatures, Room Temperatures and Occupants' Thermal Comfort in the Meeting Room resulted from the proposed algorithm implementation.

The most remarkable feature of the three temperature diagrams is the fact that both HVAC and Room temperatures present the same orbit with the temperature set-points and follow the same tension of modification, despite of their different momentary alterations. Additionally, although the Room temperature has a delayed response to the HVAC temperature set-points, it is observed that it has a decreasing inclination even more than 1°C.

Fig. 2. Room Temperatures and Occupants' Thermal Comfort in the Meeting Room resulted from the proposed algorithm implementation.

According to the thermal comfort analysis, adjusted to the examined room, the optimal value of the PMV is found around 25°C. Therefore, the set-points take appropriate values to lead to HVAC temperatures around 25°C, as presented in Fig. 1. In practice, this is the most influential factor, since it affects the PMV, which is defined as the performance criterion with the highest priority in the HVAC system control.

In Fig. 2 the dependence between the occupants' thermal comfort and the Room temperature is reflected. It is obvious that any alteration to the temperature leads to the exact opposite change to the occupants' thermal comfort.

In conclusion, it is observed that our proposed system manages to keep the Room temperatures in such values that correspond to the occupants' thermal comfort satisfaction, which is our highest priority.

The influence of our proposed system is clearly illustrated in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, where the Room temperatures and the occupants' thermal comfort are presented respectively on the one hand from the implementation of our algorithm (red) and on the other hand without any intervention (blue). In both cases initial environmental conditions were the same and we initialized the temperature set-point at 28°C.

Fig. 3. Room Temperature in the Meeting Room resulted from the proposed algorithm implementation and without any control of the HVAC system.

Fig. 4. Occupants' Thermal Comfort resulted with no control of the HVAC system and Occupants' Thermal Comfort incurred by the proposed control of the HVAC system.

In both cases the room was occupied for the period 14:00-15:00. In the first case, where the system configured automatically the room temperature (red), the occupants didn't intervene to the HVAC system operation, while in the second case (blue) they decreased the temperature set-point at 25°C. Afterwards, they left the room remaining the temperature set-point at 27°C in order to preserve the indoor conditions comfortable for their next meeting. According to the Fig. 4 the occupants' thermal comfort is always higher in the first case only except from the time frame of the meeting when the occupants' intervention took place. However, despite the fact that the comfort in the first scenario was lower during this period, the occupants didn't make any complaint and thus they didn't alter the temperature set-point. After this period, with the stable set point at 27°C in the second scenario the Room Temperature was gradually increasing and therefore the occupants' thermal comfort was similarly falling down. On the other side, in the first scenario the decreasing room temperature led to a rising thermal comfort satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an alternative in the optimization of the HVAC control system is proposed. It constitutes an

alternative, which integrates the occupants' thermal comfort and the electrical consumption of the HVAC in the same objective function and optimizes its operation according to the impact these two criteria are defined to have to this operation. The integration of these two criteria is fulfilled by their dynamic weights implementation, which are calculated in a fully determined way. Experimental results proved that this alternative can lead to an optimized HVAC operation satisfying the demand of the occupants comfort.

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